

POWERFUL TECHNIQUES FOR WRITING DICTATION

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Annotation: this article is devoted to role of dictation in a contemporary world and diverse techniques of dictation and their peculiarities.

Writing is become an essential part of modern life. Larger amounts of information must be conveyed and stored as society grows advanced. Written language becomes essential tool for this, therefore, transforms into biggest categories of communicative activity.

It is also a crucial teaching tool as it helps to strengthen and integrate the other language abilities—speaking, listening, and reading. The ability to communicate well in writing fosters competency in spoken language usage. However, it should be emphasized that productive writing is a separate linguistic action and should be taught as such.

At the same time, productive writing is an independent speech activity and should be taught as a skill in its own right. Nowadays, English as a foreign language is formally taught from elementary school to university in order to prepare students to face the globalization era.

In school, pupils actively study English for almost nine years, but most of them still face difficulties in writing something in English properly. Nowadays, asking students to write in another language, whether, it is an essay, article or creative fiction, is almost the hardest thing a teacher can ask for. However, the course should be taught to students and can not be ignored. As G.V. Rogova claims, writing as a skill is very important in both teaching and learning a foreign language; it helps pupils to assimilate letters and sounds of English language, its vocabulary and grammar, to develop habits and skills in pronunciation, speaking

and reading as well. She also points out that the practical value of writing is great because it can fix patterns of all kinds (graphemes, words, phrases and sentences) in pupils' memory, thus producing a powerful effect on their mind [197].

Therefore, the school syllabus reads "Writing is a mighty means of teaching a foreign language." Writing includes penmanship, spelling and composition. The latter is the aim of learning to write. The school syllabus states: "Pupils are expected to be able to write a letter in the foreign language within the material learnt".

In this part of our article, we want to share some of our ideas about using effective technologies and almost forgotten and rarely used writing dictation. We discovered ten reasons of writing dictation according to P. Davis and M. Rinvoluchri in their book entitled "Dictation" .[2002, 13p.]

1. The students are active during the exercise.
2. The students are active after the exercise.
3. Dictation leads to oral communicative activities.
4. Dictation fosters unconscious' thinking.
5. Dictation copes with mixed ability groups.
6. Dictation deals with large groups.
7. Dictation will often calm groups.
8. Dictation is safe for the non-native teacher.
9. For English, it is a technically useful exercise.
10. Dictation gives access to interesting text.

Unfortunately, most teachers never use dictation in teaching writing, because it takes much time to check and correct mistakes. After a thorough investigation of the given topic, we think the following types of dictation and effective technologies in performing it can be suggested. They are not something absolutely new but still interesting forms of dictation, which can be very helpful in teaching writing effectively.

Past Ending Dictation

Put the following columns on the board and ask your students to write

them in their notebook:

T	D	ID
\t\	\d\	\,d\

Dictate regular past tense verbs that your students know, asking them to write them in the appropriate column. Give each verb only once. If they don't understand it, mime it. Have students compare with each other and correct spelling mistakes. Then get them to dictate the words back to you. You write them in the appropriate column on the board.

Connections

Tell the students that you are going to dictate some words to them (for the down to write) that are connected with each other in one way. When they think they have the connection, they should shout it out and explain it. When they have the correct answer, spelling and meaning can be checked. As a follow up activity, students can generate their own lists and dictate them to the class. Here are some possible lists:

1. Picture, button, interference, channel, aerial, news (television)
2. Ink, lick, line, love, open, class, box, yours, stamp (post)
3. Wall, paper, road, colour, country, measure, find, far, book, equator (map)

Whistling Dictation

In this exercise, a teacher replaces certain words with a whistle, (or clap or tap on the desk). This type of dictation makes students think hard about the meaning of what they hear and not just how to write it down. When James Bond got back to (whistle) hotel room// it was midnight. // His windows (whistle) closed // and the air-conditioning was (whistle). // Bond switched it (whistle) and opened the windows.// His heart was still thumping (whistle) his chest.//

[Headway Pre –intermediate by John and Liz Soars]

Running Dictation

Students are put into pairs. A short text is placed, ideally, outside the classroom. One member of the pair has to “run” up to the text, memorize as

much as of it as possible, then run back to his partner and tell them what he or she read. The seated partner has to write down what he or she is told. This is repeated until the whole text has been dictated. The first pair to finish are the winners.

Picture Dictation

Students are put into pairs. One person from each pair is given a simple picture (which they must not show to their partner) and is asked to describe it to them. The person who is listening must try to draw what he is told. When the activity has finished they can compare the original picture with the drawing. The second partner is then given a different picture and the same procedure is repeated.

Mutual Dictation

This exercise involves students in combining two-part texts into one continuous piece. **Without looked** at each other's sheets. A dictates and B writes, Then B dictates A writes, and so on until the text is completed. Finally, the students show each other their sheets to check accuracy.

Text A

It was a ----- and the bus was ----- . There was a tall, handsome man standing ----- .Sitting ----- him there was a ----- . The ----- still ----- a long----- to make. He -----talking to the --- --. He tells----- that he is very wealthy. ----- pricks ----- up. He talks to her -----: she looks at him ----- . ----- tells her ----- and ----- . She ----- him with tender----- . Finally he tells her he ----- a ----- . The man says: “-----the bus at ----- -- --, then we ----- .” ----- up and gets ----- the bus. ----- does not ----- . -----has taken-----!

Text B

-----very hot day ----- very crowded.----- ----- near the front of the bus. ----- near ----- beautiful girl. -----man----- had ----- journey----- begins----- girl.----- her ears -----, ----- about his big farm: ----- with real interest. He ----- that he is sad ----- lonely. -- -- looks at ----- sympathy. ----- needs ----- wife. -----: “Let's get off ----- the next stop, -----can talk.” She gets ----- off----- . She ----- look behind her. He ----- her seat!

As you can see, all these types of dictation provide students with highly motivated participation within the lesson and simultaneously teaches a new material or fix the past one easily. Moreover, it gives a teacher a wonderful opportunity to verify methods of teaching and assessment.

Concluding our article, we may firmly state that writing is a powerful means in mastering a foreign language and underestimating of writing leads to poor results in language learning. Throughout the language experience writing offers a means for ensuring total student participation on an individual basis in developing and improving such skills as listening, understating, reproducing and improvising. In addition, writing different types of dictation can be essential part of modern teaching, saying nothing of its undoubted effectiveness.

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